

Visiting the margins
INnovative CULTural ToUrisM in European peripheries

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Executive Summary

This deliverable summarises the dissemination and communication activities conducted during the whole execution of the INCULTUM project in the frame of work package 2 (WP2). It provides the overview of the work carried out, with links to their evidence (presentations, photos, demos, published articles, posts, etc.).

The target audiences of the INCULTUM project cover a wide range of actors: action groups, associations, and networks active in the fields of cultural tourism, regional and local authorities, public administrations, political decision makers, cultural heritage institutions (museums, archives, libraries and galleries), culture and creativity enterprises, educational institutions, artists and practitioners, academic and research organizations. The impact of the project and the exploitation of the results, directly depend on the availability and visibility that the projects results have towards such a vast community of interested parties.

In this light, the work carried out by WP2 plays a central role in the implementation of the project, representing the point where the outputs produced by the pilots (WP5) and by the other work packages (WP3-WP4-WP6-WP7) are communicated and made available to its audiences, providing external visibility to the project and to its progresses, and preparing for future use and re-use of the results.

Main activities in the first year consisted in the set-up of the communication and dissemination plan and the development of the main instruments for the project outreach, mainly the website and the INCULTUM blog.

During the second year, as a follow-up of the recommendations received at the first Technical Review, a revision of the website was conducted to enrich the webpages with iconographic materials and further information material dedicated to the promotion of the activities carried out. In addition, a more structured approach to the communication and dissemination plan was agreed in the consortium, in particular regarding the work done at pilot level. Finally, the design of the Training Portal was completed and documented in the re-submission of D6.1.

The third year was devoted to completing the online delivery of contents provided in the INCULTUM Training Portal, the production of communication and promotional products, and the organisation of the final conference in Guadix on 12/4/2024. The final conference was complemented by a poster gallery exhibited in the location of the conference and promoted online with a dedicated digital poster gallery.

Several communication and dissemination actions were performed to accompany the project's progress, participating in a range of international 3rd-party events and publishing news on the project's blog.

All the materials, including publications, posters and presentations was gathered in the community space created on Zenodo, to maintain a public access to the results of the project. The description of the creation of the Zenodo community is extensively elaborated in D1.4. The final version of the Data Management Plan (D3.4) mentions the creation and discusses the management of data in Zenodo.

The current document is composed by this Executive Summary and 7 chapters:

- Chapter 1 Introduction
- Chapter 2 INCULTUM visual identity and web presence
- Chapter 3 Web presence
- Chapter 4 Events
- Chapter 5 Communication and dissemination materials
- Chapter 6 Monitoring and KPIs
- Chapter 7 Conclusions

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Scope of the deliverable

This deliverable is produced by WP2 Communication and Dissemination.

WP2 is the work package dedicated to communication and dissemination of the project. Its main objective is to spread awareness of the activities carried out by the consortium, to promote the results of the project among the members of the INCULTUM consortium, and toward projects, organisations and initiatives that participate in the INCULTUM community.

The activities of WP2 contributed to maintain a constant flow of information among the partners and to maximize the project's impact by involving stakeholders and users outside of the project's consortium. In this light, the work focused on the following lines:

- To communicate INCULTUM news and results to the widest audience
- To draw lessons to be shared in targeted communities
- To establish collaborations and to expand the INCULTUM network of common interest
- To prepare for exploitation and adoption of project results, contributing to the production of effective multiplier effects

The scope of this document is to illustrate the work done and the results achieved in the frame of the communication and dissemination activities undertaken, with links to their evidence.

The outputs achieved relate to the case studies about cultural tourism in the European peripheries carried in the pilots of WP5, data analysis and statistics carried out in WP3, development of policy recommendations and participatory models carried out in WP4, creation of training resources, networking and collaborations established in WP6, and the stakeholders mapping, impact assessment and exploitation planning of WP7.

Furthermore, WP2 has played a fundamental role in creating a factual cohesion among the partners, to let them know each other, to establish collaborations and exchanges, and in general to support WP1 in the internal communication within the consortium.

In this light, WP2 is strictly connected with the rest of the project because it has granted sharing of information, visibility and promotion to the results produced by the other WPs, within the project and in the outside network.

Figure 1 Articulation of INCULTUM work packages (from the Description of Work)

Communication and dissemination took place via a combination of online and in presence activities. The website and the blog have been the most important online instruments. The organisation of workshops, local encounters and seminars, the participation in the events organised by the participants in the network of common interest established around the project, surveys, participatory initiatives, and interviews conducted as part of the pilots, and the final international conference in Guadix represent the activities in presence. Publications, reports, presentations, posters, books and articles on scientific journals belong to the project's literature, all available as open access.

All the **deliverables** produced in the project were disseminated via WP2:

- Public deliverables are available for download from the dedicated area of the website
- Confidential deliverables are accessible to the partners only, in the Repository of the Reserved area

Furthermore, the [Zenodo INCULTUM Community](#) gathers together and provide permanent access to publications, datasets, presentations, posters, and many other resources.

Beyond the access to public deliverables and other digital resources on the project's website and on the Zenodo INCULTUM Community, the communication and the promotion of all the other products and initiatives of the project took place through a rich **programme of events** organized locally by the pilot coordinators. Started in the first year, they continued in the second and third years. These events offered the opportunity to present and discuss the results of the innovation actions, through an extended dialogue between the consortium members and the local stakeholders.

In addition, two project's **international events** and two **networking sessions** were delivered and promoted:

- The Data Workshop, held online in March 2022
- The Workshop held in the frame of the Euromed 2022 Conference in Limassol (Cyprus)
- The Workshop held in the frame of the ESRA Congress 2023 in Alicante (Spain)
- The final International Conference, held in Guadix in April 2024 as a hybrid event

The **online communication** and dissemination channels and the infrastructure tool developed in the first months of the project were used and further developed to promote the project's activities. Workshops,

seminars, local and international events (online and in presence) were announced in dedicated news on the blog.

Direct **contacts with stakeholders** were activated to run the pilots.

A wider visibility of the project was also possible thanks to the **collaborations with European organizations and projects**. This was in the scope of the participation of INCULTUM representatives in the events organised by 3rd parties, which were promoted on the website and through the project's blog, too.

The combination of all the activities introduced above have been at the heart of the creation of a vivid **network of common interest**, which is at the basis of further exploitation of project's results, beyond the end of the EU funding period. The INCULTUM Network is further discussed in the deliverable D6.3.

1.2 Overview of the communication and dissemination action

This report aims to provide a comprehensive view of the communication and dissemination activities implemented during the whole project life, from month 1 to month 36.

As illustrated in the report of the EU about communication, dissemination and exploitation¹ important differences exist between communication and dissemination and their relationship with impact delivery and exploitation.

Impacts and exploitation are addressed in a different deliverable ([D7.3 : Updated plan for the impact, evaluation and exploitation of results](#)) and for this reason we do not enter into the details concerning this matter, in this document.

The role of communication and dissemination is distinguished because of their links with impact. The approaches taken by INCULTUM to this regard are the following:

- Communication aimed to inform, promote, and communicate the project's activities and its results to stakeholders, citizens, local action groups, associations and any other interested party
- Dissemination aimed to contribute to maximise the impact by making available as open access the knowledge and resources produced in the project to those who can benefit, use and re-use these results

Taking into account the two different scopes, nevertheless communication and dissemination share the same instruments, namely:

- Online tools
- Events
- Publications

One major difference is the duration of the availability of the resources: for the communication, updated information has been provided during the whole EU funding period, from the start until the end of the action; for the dissemination, the resources created in the project shall remain available beyond the end of the EU funding period. To this regard, the main repository of resources is represented by the Zenodo INCULTUM Community and the INCULTUM blog hosted on digitalmeetsculture.net magazine where news from the pilots will continue to be published. Furthermore, the website will remain available as it exists by the end of the project, for at least 4 more years.

The initial reflection about the liaison between communication, dissemination and exploitation plan was covered in deliverable D2.2.

More detailed reflections about the impact dimension of the dissemination are elaborated in the frame of WP7

¹ European Commission, European Research Executive Agency, *Communication, dissemination & exploitation what is the difference and why they all matter*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2023, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2848/289075>

Impact, evaluation and exploitation plan and provided in the deliverable D7.3 Updated plan for the impact, evaluation and exploitation of results that describes how the scientific results of the project are conceived as a common good. To this regard, it is worth noting the contribution represented by the INCULTUM Book published with Routledge publisher, reported in deliverable D2.4, which aims to contribute to the advancement of knowledge in the domain of cultural tourism and social sustainability. The Book will be a relevant instrument for scholars and stakeholders to go a step forward in their innovation practices and research.

Intermediate internal reporting was carried out at the end of the first and second year to assess the progresses in the field and to adopt possible re-focusing strategy and updated approaches. A review of the communication and dissemination approaches took place as a follow-up of the recommendations received at the first technical review, held on 15/5/2022.

A synthesis of the communication and dissemination activities carried out during the three years of the project duration is provided in the tables below, to offer an overview of the evolution that the communication and dissemination had along all the whole project's duration.

Activities during the first year in summary:

- Design of INCULTUM logo
- Initial design of visual identity
- Domain registration, set-up of the development environment and creation of the project's website
- Set-up of the project's blog
- Templates and initial dissemination materials (factsheet and general presentation)
- Launch of the first project's newsletter
- First edition of the Training Portal published as pages of the project's website
- Support to endorsement and dissemination of the Data Workshop, in collaboration with the event's leader SDU
- Networking effort for establishing collaboration with other projects to support the creation of a stakeholder community
- Liaisons with project partners to stimulate sharing of information. A particular effort was devoted to fostering collaboration and dialogue with the INCULTUM Pilots.
- Deliverable D2.1 Online presence
- Deliverable D2.2 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan
- Reporting mechanism put in place and information collected in a reporting sheet that all partners continued to update regularly.

Activities during the second year in summary:

- Review of the project's visual appearance on the website
- Re-design of the structure of the Training Portal
- Continuous publication of news on the INCULTUM Blog
- Continuous updates of the contents of the website
- Production of the collection of pilot posters, distribution to the partners, presentation in public events and encounters, and publication of the digital versions on the website
- Collaborations established with new members of the network of common interest
- Participation in 3rd party events
- Organisation of the Networking Session on Cultural Tourism at Euromed 2022 Conference
- Launch of the 2nd and 3rd Newsletters

Activities during the third year in summary:

- Continuous publication of news on the INCULTUM Blog
- Continuous updates of the contents of the website
- Creation of the Innovation space on the website
- Creation of the Policy Toolbox space on the website
- Enrichment of the contents in the Training Portal
- Publication of the new course on social branding and of the book on participatory approaches and governance in culture in the Training Portal
- Creation of the Multilingual pages
- Participation in 3rd party events
- Organisation of the Networking Session on Participatory Approaches in Tourism and Sustainable Development at ERSA 2023 Conference
- Launch of the 4th Newsletter to 246 recipients
- Organisation of the Final International Conference in Guadix, on 12/4/2024, including poster gallery

The following chapters provide further details about the activities and the results achieved in the field of communication and dissemination.

2 INCULTUM VISUAL IDENTITY

Because of the themes of INCULTUM, the visual identity was designed for being appealing to different audiences and not limiting the first view to a unique target configuration. The use of imagery has been particularly adopted. In this light, the website is rich in photographs complemented by descriptive information that is then focusing more deeply on individual interests. Such approach, with visuals and texts equally balanced, is replicated in the various dissemination tools that the project produced such as blogs, publications, presentations, posters, etc...

The visual identity for INCULTUM, marked with a unique and easily identifiable brand, includes the following elements: the INCULTUM logo and the INCULTUM tagline

These two elements have been adopted on all the communication products to create a consistent message. They have been at the basis of the layout design of project's website, the project's blog hosted on digitalmeetsculture.net magazine, the publications about the project and its pilots, the newsletter and the collection of posters illustrating many different views of the pilot sites involved in the experimental innovation actions.

2.1 INCULTUM logo

Different coloured versions of the logo exist to be used in the various communication products to be realised along the project lifetime.

Figure 2 INCULTUM logo

2.2 Tagline

The INCULTUM tagline is a short phrase associated with the company name. It represents the company's global approach to its products and services. It has been associated with the project and its various initiatives. It has been conceived to be clear, precise, and indicative, able to capture attention and easy to remember. It has not been thought to summarize services or products, but instead to convey the values that the project aims to deliver, ideally lasting for a longer time and not just for the EU funding period. It encapsulates the INCULTUM project's name plus keywords that summarise what INCULTUM stands for, in concise terms.

Visiting the margins: innovative cultural tourism in European peripheries

Community identity, tourism as a tool, innovation

The concept of tourism as a tool is at the core of the innovations experimented and developed in the INCULTUM pilots. This tagline also became the title of the promotional publication delivered at the conference of Guadix.

3 WEB PRESENCE

The web presence of INCULTUM is successfully achieved via the tools that are described in detail the following paragraphs, namely: the project's website and the blog. They were created since the beginning of the project and have been kept updated, in collaboration with partners. Along the whole project lifetime, 95 pages were created on the website and 210 news were published on the INCULTUM blog.

The INCULTUM website and the blog are implemented with WordPress Content Management System, an open source publishing platform licensed under the GNU General Public License (GPL). At the end of the EC funding period, the partner Promoter, leader of the WP2 Communication and Dissemination, is committed to keep the website and the blog accessible online for at least 4 years after the conclusion of the project.

Social media accounts have been created to support the communication actions. The most used social media is the YouTube channel that hosts the videos of the data workshop and of the academic course on social branding. X (former Twitter) and Instagram are also open to rebound the news from the blog.

Furthermore, in collaboration with the Data Management Plan, the INCULTUM Community has been created on the Zenodo platform to provide access to the datasets, publications, presentations, posters, and reports delivered during the project. Such Community is intended to represent the legacy of the project publicly accessible and sustainable in the time. More information about the Zenodo INCULTUM Community is provided in the Final Public Report D1.4 and in the Data Management Plan deliverable D3.4.

3.1 Project's website

www.incultum.eu

The website is the cornerstone for the project communication and dissemination, serving the aim of promoting the project activities and results and outcomes to a wide audience, and providing visibility to the ten Pilots. Additionally, it serves as an internal collaborative space for the project's partners by embedding a reserved area for the exchange of documents and repository.

The project's website was launched at the very beginning of the project with a first publication in May 2021, and its draft was presented to the consortium at the kick-off meeting. Its idea about visual identity, the structure of the website, basic content and preliminary information were discussed and approved by the partners, who were also involved in the editorial process by providing to responsible partner Promoter initial texts and images to populate the website pages. Since then, the sections of the website have been constantly developed and populated with updated information, with periodic revision of the sections and their articulation. The collection of pictures of the pilot sites was the result of visits and encounters carried out at each site.

For the duration of the project's life, the project continued to:

- Update constantly the content and the design of the website to reflect project's progress
- Make project materials and other documentation available for the project's audience in the public area
- Maintain updated the information in the Reserved area for the use of the partners

The description of the structure of the website presented in this section reflects the final outcome of the project, which is what is left as legacy and maintained accessible in the coming years.

Figure 3 Website structure

HOME PAGE

The home page is composed by three parts:

1. The slider that highlights the latest achievements
2. The links to the latest communication products available for download
3. The key features of the projects linking to the specific sections of the website

The three parts are regularly updated to provide information and links, inspiring the visitor to browse through the website, fostering them to discover more about the project. The structure of the home page has been reviewed along the whole project, offering to the user the immediate feeling of the living character of the website, avoiding the impression of being static, and responding to the recommendation provided by the reviewers at the first technical review at the end of the first year of project's life.

Slider

The slider in the home page has changed with updated highlights about the latest news from the projects, linking with the relevant sections of the website.

The latest highlights of the slider are illustrated in the figure below.

Figure 4 Home page slider

Latest communication products

Following the slider, the second part of the home page is dedicated to the latest products.

Key features

The third part of the home page provides links to the most relevant features of the project.

HORIZONTAL MENU

The horizontal menu is displayed at the top of all the webpages, giving access to the main parts of the website.

Figure 5 Horizontal menu

The 'Innovation' and the 'Policies' items bring each one to a dedicated comprehensive page

'Innovation' page of the website

The 'Innovation' page aims to present the approach about innovation pursued in INCULTUM .

Figure 6 'Innovation' landing page of the website

It also provides access to the innovation fact sheets produced by the pilots to present their individual proposed and experimented innovations.

Figure 7 Innovation factsheets

'Policies' page of the website

The 'Policies' page aims to present the policy tools that constitute the INCULTUM Policy Toolbox:

- Two think papers
- Two Policy briefs
- The Joint Policy recommendations produced by the projects funded under the same Horizon 2020 call, representing the outcomes of the Policy Round Table organised by the EU.

Figure 8 'Policies' page of the website

The menu items 'About', 'Pilots', 'Training' and 'Dissemination & Networking' are structured with submenu, as illustrated in the figure below.

Figure 9 Sub-menus

'About' section of the website

The 'About' section aims to provide information about the project and its consortium.

Figure 10 About landing page

The 'About' submenu provides links to the following specific pages:

- Objectives
- Work packages
- Partners
- Contact details

The last item of the submenu brings to the Reserved area that is protected by a password and used by the partners for their internal repository of documents

'Pilots' section of the website

The 'Pilots' section of the website aims to provide contents about the pilot approaches and their outcomes.

Figure 11 Pilots landing page

The 'Pilots' landing page introduces the overall scope of the pilots in INCULTUM.

The ‘Pilots’ submenu provides links to the individual pages dedicated to each pilot, which include a selection of the most relevant news from the pilot (more detailed news are provided through the blog), pictures, posters, contacts, etc. The individual pages contain a mix of text and images, designed to be more attractive for the attention of the reader.

Figure 12 Excerpts from the pilot individual pages

‘Training’ section of the website

The ‘Training’ section of the website is the Training Portal that is conceived as a gate that gives access to different types of resources. It is designed as a delivery vehicle where the user can get resources and information, organized in two main areas:

- Professional training and academic offer
- Studies, guidelines and tools

Figure 13 INCULTUM Training Portal

The professional training section is based on the outcomes of local training activities conducted by the pilots in their respective territories. Due to the diverse characteristics, needs, and activities of the pilots, various types of training actions are presented on the portal, including materials in local languages. These activities target local stakeholders and communities, public administrators, tourism professionals, and cultural managers.

The academic offering section caters to university students, researchers, and professionals engaged in lifelong learning. The contents have been curated by the University of Pisa, Matej Bell University in Slovakia, and Uppsala University. This offering encompasses an array of resources, including an online course on marketing and social branding, a book focusing on participatory governance and models in culture and cultural tourism, and an on-site program comprising doctoral courses, seminars, and lectures delivered in 2022, documented through their syllabi.

Both the local training and the academic offerings present clear indication of the intended targets

The studies, guidelines, and tools section gathers resources in different formats to allow users to explore principles of data management, test digital tools, review models of participation, and learn about public policies supporting territorial development and sustainable tourism.

In addition, a bibliography extracted from the deliverables produced during the INCULTUM project, and an orientation service providing answers to frequently asked questions, complement the two training areas.

The implementation of the portal is featured by a dedicated logo and each page of the 'Training' section indicates the path to move around in the various areas.

A more extensive description of the structure of the Training Portal is provided in the deliverable D6.1.

Further information about the training contents and their promotion within the INCULTUM network is provided in deliverable D6.3.

'Dissemination & Networking' section of the website

The 'Dissemination & Networking' section aims to provide contents about the actions put in place for the outreach campaign developed during the whole project, organising workshops and local seminars, participating in networking events, and producing a wide range of communication products.

Figure 14 Dissemination and Networking landing page

The 'Dissemination and Networking' landing page starts with an introductory text that provides links to most relevant elements of communication products, namely: latest publications, events, and posters.

Figure 15 Preview of the latest publications in the ‘Dissemination and Networking’ landing page

Then, the ‘Dissemination and Networking’ submenu provides links to the following specific areas:

- Networking
- Events
- Multilingual pilot presentations
- Press kit
- Posters
- Newsletters
- Public deliverables

Further details about the Networking section of the website are provided in deliverable D6.3 INCULTUM Network.

‘Events’ section of the website

The Events section of the website aims to provide information about the programme of international, local, and networking events.

Figure 16 Events landing page

The section is composed by the landing page and the sub-menu pointing to 4 individual pages dedicated to the Data Workshop, the two INCULTUM networking sessions at Euromed 2022 Conference and ESRA 2023 Congress, and the International Conference in Guadix.

Further information about the INCULTUM events is provided in chapter 4 below.

‘Multilingual pilot presentations’ page

This Multilingual pilot presentations’ page provides links to the individual pages that present the pilot’s descriptions in local languages.

Figure 17 Multilingual pilot presentations

The scope of the multilingual pages is to offer to the local communications engaged and interested in the pilots to have an introduction in their own language, enlarging the local audiences and acknowledging the cultural value of the European multilingualism.

'Press kit' page of the website

The 'Press kit' page provides a collection of links to the INCULTUM communication products. The preview of a selection of products is also provided.

Figure 18 Press kit page on the website

The Press kit page starts with the links to the pages where factsheets, policy recommendations, foresights, newsletter and presentations are provided for download:

- Innovation page
- Policy page
- Newsletter page
- International Conference page
- Pilots pages

Then, specific areas of the page provide links to materials that have a relevance at project's level:

- Books
- Posters
- Project's factsheet and general presentation
- Presentations delivered in 3rd party conferences

Further information about the contents of the products linked by the 'Press kit' page is provided in Chapter 5 below.

'Poster' section of the website

The 'Poster' section provide access to the posters developed during the project.

Figure 19 'Posters' landing page

The 'Posters' landing page links to the individual pages where the posters are downloadable:

- The collection of the Pilot posters
- The collection of posters exhibited in the occasion of the International Conference in Guadix
- The general INCULTUM poster
- The poster developed to promote the International Conference in Guadix.

Further information about the contents of the posters is provided in section 5.2 below.

'Newsletters' page of the website

The 'Newsletters' page provides the links to the 4 INCULTUM Newsletters.

Figure 20 Newsletter landing page

Further information about the INCULTUM newsletters is provided in section 3.4 'Mailing list and newsletters', below.

'Public deliverables' section of the website

The 'Public deliverables' section provides a table with links to the public documents that are stored in the INCULTUM Zenodo Community.

3.2 Project's blog

<https://www.digitalmeetsculture.net/projects/incultum-blog/>

Scope of the blog is to maintain a lively communication channel, combining news from the project and more general information about the themes of the values of culture, community identity, cultural heritage and digital cultural heritage, which are developed within initiatives outside the project, mostly those of the associate partners.

The project's blog is hosted on Digitalmeetsculture.net, which is the official media partner of INCULTUM project. Digitalmeetsculture.net is an interactive online magazine, officially registered in Italy, which exists since 2010 providing visibility to initiatives connected with culture and arts. Digitalmeetsculture.net is a valuable information tool with a selected, high-profile audience. The portal receives c 25,000 visitors per month and is gaining significance in the global digital cultural heritage community, thus offering an added value for the communication and dissemination of INCULTUM.

The look of the INCULTUM blog was designed to be consistent with the visual identity of the project.

Figure 21 INCULTUM blog landing page

The posts that are published in the blog appear on the website via a feed RSS. The 10 most recent news from the feed are displayed on the right column of each page of the website. Then, news published on digitalmeetsculture.net are posted on the X (former Twitter) account of the magazine, which currently counts over 1,100 followers.

Because of the difficulty to reach withing the limited time of the project's duration, visibility on the social media, the rebound of the news on the account of the magazine represents an additional way to support the project's

communication, offering an extra channel next to the social media of the consortium partners.

To-date, 210 posts are published on the INCULTUM blog about the project's progress and its pilots.

Figure 22 RSS Feed from the blog to the website

The publication of news on the INCULTUM blog is continuing, as demonstrated by the initiative held by Portugal, Slovakia and Sicily in the last days of April 2024 and the new events already planned on 20 May 2024 in Garfagnana to promote the pilot of San Pellegrino in Alpe, and in October 2024 in Seville to promote the pilots in Campina de Faro.

3.3 Social media

The social media channels of the project were opened in the first half of 2022.

Figure 23 INCULTUM channels on the social media

The YouTube channel is used to provide access to two playlists that contain the full recording of the data workshop and the course on marketing and social branding. The playlists are linked to the pages of the website and are used mostly as the cloud storage of the videos.

A general consideration is worth to mentioned regarding the channels on the X and on the Instagram platforms. The worldwide use of the social media has changed. We are all submerged by social media posts and this is diminishing their actual usefulness for the project's communication towards the articulated professional audience targeted by INCULTUM. The effort to achieve wide visibility on the social media is becoming an endeavour per se, that requires dedicated and specialised resources that were not planned at the time in the original design of the project. Social media are used to communicate political messages, commercial advertising, and the role of the influencers became a new challenge for the effective use of social media. For the future, we plan to maintain the INCULTUM social media channels where we published already news during the project. The social media were somehow useful to contribute to sharing news about the local activities to wider international audience. However, being impossible to expect to gain visibility that can compete with the number of followers generated by other players in this kind of communication channels, and because of the specialistic expertise that would be necessary for an effective marketing of the channels, we do not plan to invest more on this type of communication at project level in the future.

3.4 Mailing list and newsletters

The digital presence of INCULTUM is complemented by the creation of a mailing list to collect contacts from INCULTUM Stakeholders Group and interested followers and a project's digital newsletter.

Since the early days of the project, efforts were made for creating a stakeholder base, to be contacted via a dedicated mailing list that is incultum-network@promoter.it. E-mail addresses that are part of the mailing list were either collected via the contact form available on the project website or provided individually by INCULTUM partners upon consent of the concerned person. The mailing list grew from the 101 recipients addressed in the first newsletter to 246 recipients of today.

Because of the rules of the GDPR, the mailing list has been created for the scope of the communication of INCULTUM, under the responsibility of the partner Promoter. For this reason, it cannot be shared with other users. After the final technical review, a final message is planned to be sent to all the recipients to inform them about the conclusion of the INCULTUM project and inviting them to register to the new initiatives that are expected to come out from the INCULTUM experience, at local and at European levels.

The mailing list has been used for the distribution of the [INCULTUM Newsletter](#). Four Newsletters have been issued along the project.

Figure 24 INCULTUM Newsletters

The [first Newsletter](#) was issued in February 2022 to announce the launch of the website and to promote the Data Workshop. That was also the occasion to introduce the readers to the main topics aimed to be developed by the project – namely: pilots, policies and training – and to highlight some of the members of the INCULTUM Network.

The [second Newsletter](#) was issued in October 2022 to announce the re-design of the INCULTUM Training Portal, to promote the first Policy Brief on Sustainable Tourism, to announce the Cultural Tourism Workshop at EUROMED 2022, to continue to provide news from the INCULTUM Network and to highlight the results from the INCULTUM pilots.

The [third Newsletter](#) was issued in May 2023 focusing on the Innovation factsheets produced by each pilot, the new resources published on the INCULTUM Training Portal, to announce the International Conference on Cultural Tourism Advances co-organised by INCULTUM in Leuven, and to continue to promote the pilots achievements and the news from the INCULTUM Network.

The [fourth Newsletter](#) was issued in April 2024 to announce the International Conference in Guadix, to promote the four major publications produced by INCULTUM in the last year, namely: the dissemination book *VISITING THE MARGINS: COMMUNITY IDENTITY, TOURISM AS A TOOL, INNOVATION* distributed at the conference and available as open access, the academic book *PARTICIPATORY GOVERNANCE AND MODELS IN CULTURE AND CULTURAL*, the online academic course on *MARKETING AND SOCIAL BRANDING IN TOURISM DESTINATIONS*

TOURISM, and the *GUIDELINES ON THE USE OF EUROPEAN STRUCTURAL AND INVESTMENT FUNDS*.

The Newsletters are available online via the dedicated page on the website that provides previews and links to the documents accessible via the Zenodo INCULTUM Community.

A final Newsletter is planned to be produced to accompany the farewell message, promoting the recent publication of the Policy Toolbox as the instrument to support new multiplying initiatives in the future.

3.5 INCULTUM on the Web

This section of the report provides an overview of how INCULTUM has been reflected by the websites of 3rd parties.

The first aspect is the acknowledgement received by the EC on the CORDIS platform.

INCULTUM is published since the early days on the CORDIS website of the EC at

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101004552>

Figure 25 INCULTUM factsheet on CORDIS

Furthermore, a new 'Results Pack' has been published online by CORDIS about the results of the projects funded in Horizon 2020 on the theme of cultural tourism. The title of new publication is "Conserving culture and cultural heritage through inclusive and sustainable development". In the frame of the 'Results Pack', together with its sister projects, INCULTUM is presented with a dedicated article titled "Local communities and stakeholders give cultural tourism a boost in Europe's periphery".

Figure 26 INCULTUM article in the CORDIS 'Results pack'

The article presents the results of INCULTUM regarding participatory models and collaborative practices for cultural tourism, exploiting heritage resources as a common good, capacity building and knowledge transfer for sustainable tourism.

INCULTUM highlights are hosted as well on the websites of members of the network, namely:

- Heritage Research Hub
- SPOT Social and Innovative Platform on Cultural Tourism
- IMPACTOUR Community Platform
- UNCHARTED Community
- IN SITU LinkedIn Community
- Eureka3D Community

Further information about the networking activities carried out by INCULTUM have been in the focus of Task 6.3 Community building and networking, and are described in the deliverable D6.3 INCULTUM network.

3.6 Sustainability of the web presence of INCULTUM

As illustrated in the previous sections, the INCULTUM website and the connected blog have been fundamental instruments to channel information about the project to our targets. Having arrived at the end of the EU funding period, we have taken some decisions about the sustainability of the project's communication in the next period.

On one hand, the website will be kept alive by partner Promoter for at least 4 years after the conclusion of the

EU funding period, as part of the legacy of the project. However, it is expected to be maintained as it is and its future development is going to phase-out. The consortium decided to use the Zenodo social platform where the INCULTUM Community has been created and populated with all the datasets, presentations and publications produced during the EU funded period. The Zenodo INCULTUM Community will be the main repository to preserve and to provide access to the various types of resources created in the project. Zenodo has a clear vocation as the instrument put at the disposal of the European research community and we can rely on its use on a longer term. We have started monitoring the access to the Community as a mean to measure the actual exploitation impact of the project in the future.

On the other hand, about the future communication of INCULTUM, the blog on digitalmeetsculture.net remains active as the space to provide news about the activities that the pilots continue to carry on in their territory. The editorial team at Promoter, which is the owner and the publisher of the magazine, will be the reference for the INCULTUM pilots to receive and to publish news on the blog. As for the website, the future development of the INCULTUM social media channels is going to phase-out, even if the channels will remain open to give access to what has been posted along the EU funding period. The INCULTUM channels on YouTube, Instagram and X remain available for the partners who can use them, for possible future activities, based on their own individual projects.

4 EVENTS

Planning of project's events has been carried out by the event's leader, while Promoter supports the promotion and communication of the event.

Two international events have been organised during the project:

- The Data workshop, an online event delivered in March 2022
- The International conference, a hybrid event held in Guadix in April 2024

Furthermore, two networking events took place in 2022 and in 2023:

- The Cultural Tourism event hosted by Euromed 2022 in November 2022 in Limassol (Cyprus)
- The Role of participatory approaches in tourism and sustainable development event hosted by the ESRA Congress 2023 in August 2023 in Alicante (Spain)

In parallel, several occasions of promoting and debating the project's work were organised locally by the pilot partners.

All the events organised by the pilots have been promoted locally by the pilot coordinators, and supported by dedicated news on the INCULTUM blog, with a selection of them reported in the pages dedicated to each pilot.

Furthermore, the INCULTUM partners have been committed to participating in events organized by third parties, being presentations to conferences and to specific seminars.

A specific page in the project's website summarizes the events delivered by the project, while individual sub-pages were also created for the online Data Workshop, the International Conference in Guadix and the two networking events in Limassol and in Alicante.

4.1 Data Workshop

The Data Workshop 'Measuring the Impact of Cultural Tourism' has been the first public online event that took place on 3/3/2022 under the coordination of SDU. The event was composed of two parts: a reserved meeting where project partners shared and discussed individual methods for data collection and analysis with comments and presentations by task leader SDU and by CBS; and a public event that delivered a presentation about the project and two keynote speakers providing highly specialist lectures. The chair of the event was prof. Karol Jan Borowiecki – WP Leader, University of Southern Denmark. Overall, the event was attended by 30 participants.

The following presentations were delivered during the workshop:

- Introduction to INCULTUM project, Antonella Fresa, INCULTUM Network Coordinator, Promoter
- Cultural statistics to evidence societal and economic impact, Trilce Navarrete, Erasmus Universiteit Rotterdam
- Challenges of data analytics strategies for tourism in peripheral areas, Enrico Bertacchini, University of Turin
- Building a strong tourism value proposition, Carsten Jacob Humlebæk, Copenhagen Business School
- Data planning, monitoring, and evaluation for cultural tourism, Sara Mitchell, University of Southern Denmark

The visibility to the workshop included: publication of a dedicated page, a pre-event news on the blog, and the inclusion of the Data Workshop among the information delivered with the first project's newsletter.

Figure 27 Data Workshop

Post event information was prepared by collecting and publishing the presentations delivered by the speakers, and by editing video recordings of the presentations. The videos were then published in the YouTube channel that was opened on the occasion of the workshop.

Figure 28 Playlist of the Data Workshop registrations on YouTube

4.2 International conference

As a concluding event, the International Conference ‘Visiting the Margins: Innovative Cultural Tourism in European Peripheries’ was organised in Guadix on 12/4/2024 as an hybrid event.

The programme of the event and the presentations delivered by the speakers are provided in the dedicated page on the website and downloadable from the Zenodo INCULTUM Community.

Each section of the event combined a presentation from one of the project’s partner and an invited speaker, as it follows:

- Session 1 ‘Cultural tourism, promoting European peripheries, identity and local development’ with the interventions of Jose Maria Civantos (UGR), Coordinator of INCULTUM, UGR and Neil Forbes from Coventry University
- Session 2 ‘Innovations’ with interventions of Vincent Guichard (Bibracte), Innovation Manager of

INCULTUM and Nancy Duxbury from CES, University of Coimbra

- Session 3 'Circular cultural tourism and data' with interventions of Marco Palomeque & Karol Jan Borowiecki (SDU), Leader of Data analysis and statistics in INCULTUM and Antonia Gravagnuolo, CNR
- Session 4 'Impacts' with interventions of Carsten Jacob Humlebæk (CBS), Leader Impact, Evaluation and Exploitation plan in INCULTUM and Jesús Fernández Fernández from Universidad Oviedo & Ecomuseu La Ponte

Figure 29 Pictures from the International Conference in Guadix

The event was a great occasion for debating with vivid and very interesting questions&answers sessions. Overall, the event was attended by 50 participants in presence and 20 online. A rich poster exhibition was organised in the corridor bringing to the conference hall. All the posters and all the presentations are accessible from the dedicated pages on the website and downloadable from the Zenodo INCULTUM Community. Pre-event and post-event news have been published on the blog to promote the initiative.

The meeting in Guadix was also the occasion to discover the beauty of the landscape of the Altiplano de Granada that is the site of the pilot coordinated by UGR.

4.3 Workshop at Euromed 2022

The event was organized as an integral part of the 2022 edition of the international conference EUROMED in Limassol (Cyprus), to discuss about the role of community engagement and citizen participation in enhancing and promoting sustainable tourism in peripheral areas as valuable alternatives to mass tourism itineraries.

The workshop was organised in two parts:

- The first part introduced the themes of policies and participatory model development and the plurality of paths to market for participatory local tourism, with interventions of representatives of INCULTUM, TExTOUR and IMPACTOUR
- The second part was devoted provide highlights from the INCULTUM Pilots, with interventions of Altiplano de Granada – José Maria Martin Civantos (UGR) presenting the pilot of Altiplano de Granada, Marina Toger (UU) presenting the pilot of the Swedish archipelago, Kamila Borsekova (MBU) presenting

the pilot of Central Slovakia, John Tierny (EACTHRA) presenting the pilot in Ireland, Sotiris Tsoukarelis and Thaleia Pantoula (The High Mountains cooperative) presenting the pilot in Greece, Eglantina Serjani and Ardit Miti (CeRPHAAL) presenting the pilot in Albania, and Michela Natilli (UNIFI) presenting the pilot in Tuscany

Figure 30 INCULTUM Workshop at Euromed 2022

The very rich programme offered to the participants in the Euromed conference a rather complete overview of the innovation actions supported by the EU, with a more in-depth discussion about the INCULTUM pilots.

Overall, the event was attended by 30 participants in presence and 20 online. Programme and presentations have been published on a dedicated page on the website.

4.4 Workshop at ESRA 2023 Congress

The Special Session titled ‘The role of participatory approaches in tourism and sustainable development’ was organised by INCULTUM and held on 31/8/ 2023 in the frame of the prestigious ESRA 2023 Congress in Alicante.

Figure 31 INCULTUM Special Session at ESRA 2023 Congress

The Session brought together experts from around the world to discuss innovative strategies in sustainable tourism, featuring presentations from six different countries and offering insights into the intersection of participatory methods and sustainable tourism practices. Presenters from and beyond INCULTUM project

members, demonstrated how participatory methods, data collection, and community engagement are essential for shaping the future of responsible and sustainable tourism.

Overall, the event was attended by 30 participants in presence. Programme and presentations have been published on a dedicated page on the website.

4.5 Local encounters

The local events have been organized or attended by the INCULTUM partners to promote and to communicate the innovations experimented in the pilots. All the pilots' activities have been communicated publishing news on project's blog.

The communication at local level was managed by the Pilot coordinators, in the frame of their own pilots. UGR in its role of task leader and WP5 leader was responsible for the correct execution of the work at local level, and Promoter in its role of WP2 leader has been providing support to communicate and dissemination the pilots to a wider international audience. While the meetings and local activities organized by the Pilots with their local community and stakeholders have taken place also in local language, the activities were promoted in English on project's blogs. The news from the blog are listed in the 'Events' section of the website.

Figure 32 Excerpt from the 'Events' page and corresponding news on the blog

To support team building, to monitor the progress of Pilots, and also to collect visual materials such as photographs and videos of the various locations for use in the promotional materials, a programme of meetings took place between the WP2 leader Promoter and the Pilot Coordinators:

- Year 1: in Sicily to meet Pilot 4 (July 2021), in Portugal to meet Pilot 2 (March 2022), and in France to meet Pilot 6 (April 2022)
- Year 2: in Andalusia to meet Pilot 1 (May 2022), in Garfagnana to meet Pilot 5 (July 2022), in Slovakia to meet Pilot 3 (September 2022), in Albania to meet Pilot 8 and in Greece to meet Pilot 7 (October 2022), in Ireland to meet Pilot 9 (March 2023)
- Year 3: in Sweden to meet Pilot 10 (April 2023)

Figure 33 Pictures from the encounters between WP2 Leader the Pilot Coordinators

Out of the these encounters a wide collection of pictures was realised, then used to produce the pilot promotional posters, distributed to all the pilot partners to support the local communication and dissemination. Communication Guidelines were shared with the consortium and made available in the project’s repository together with the relevant logos to be included in the promotional materials for use by the project’s partners in their local communication efforts.

Figure 34 Communication Guidelines for pilots

Each pilot organized a wide range of local events, targeting policy makers, community groups, volunteers, public administrators, cultural institutions, stakeholders, and citizenry. In addition to specific meetings, and formal encounters, several events were organized as informal ‘get together’ and assemblies, to give the maximum opportunity of exchanges and debates among the participants.

4.6 Cultural events

The following events carried out in 2023, are worth to be mentioned for their special cultural value:

- The theatrical performances in San Pellegrino in Alpe (4 public performances)
- The debates about valuing Islamic heritage in Sicily (2 public cultural events)
- The presentations of the recovery of historical hydraulic assets and traditional cultivation techniques in Andalusia (3 public events)
- The archaeology of institutional burial in Ireland (3 public lectures)
- The promotion of voluntary tourism in Northwest Greece (5 public cultural events)

The presentations delivered by INCULTUM partners are available in the Zenodo INCULTUM Community.

4.7 Participation in third party's events

As an outcome of the contacts established in the frame of the INCULTUM Network, several cross-collaboration activities were carried out during the whole project's duration. Each of these activities was reported in dedicated news on the project's blog. They were the occasion to share information and results, contributing therefore to engage with stakeholders and experts, and to raise awareness about the EU funded project, as part of the project's communication, but also to maximise the impact of the action, and to present the scientific and innovation results achieved, as part of the project's dissemination.

Two events are worth to be mentioned for their specific relevance in terms of dissemination. They focus on the connection between sister projects funded in the ambit of the same call of Horizon 2020:

- The International Conference on Cultural Tourism
- The Policy roundtable of EU-funded projects on sustainable cultural tourism

Further details about the cross-collaboration activities are provided in deliverable D6.3 INCULTUM Network.

5 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION MATERIALS

A wide range of promotional materials were produced during the project's lifetime, including factsheets, brochures, books, posters and presentations. They are all available on the Zenodo INCULTUM Community, and linked in the concerned pages of the project's website.

The main communication and dissemination products are illustrated in the paragraphs below.

During the first year, a Project's factsheet, information sheets about the pilots, also in local language, the first Newsletter and a general presentation were produced in digital format.

Factsheets

Newsletter

General presentation

Figure 35 Communication products from the 1st year

These initial products enabled the start of the communication. The general presentation was reused and adapted to promote the project and its innovation areas in conferences and seminars.

References to all the communication and dissemination products are provided in the Press Kit page, that is linked under the 'Dissemination and Networking' item of the main horizontal menu and described in the section 3.5 above.

The following sections provide more details about the books, posters, pilots' communication products and scientific publications produced during the project.

5.1 Books

The results of the project have been presented in the Dissemination book produced by Promoter. It is a publication of 48 pages (ISBN 979-12-210-5832-1) produced on paper in 300 copies and made available as open access on the project's website and on the [Zenodo INCULTUM Community](#). The printed copies were distributed to the participants in the International Conference in Guadix and shipped to the partners for local promotion.

Figure 36 INCULTUM Dissemination book

Participatory approaches in cultural tourism have been discussed in the academic book produced by UMB. It is a digital book adopted by academic courses and available as open access on the project's website and on the Zenodo INCULTUM Community.

Figure 37 Academic book on participatory approaches in cultural tourism

The scientific INCULTUM Book is under publication with Routledge publisher. The contract for the publication has been signed by the Coordination UGR and all the chapters are already under editing by the publisher. The book is described in the deliverable D2.4.

5.2 Posters

Between the second and third year, 8 poster for each pilot (total 80 posters) were produced, provided to the partners for local communication, made available for download from the website and exhibited in the occasion of participation in 3rd party events.

Figure 38 Pilot posters

During the third year, in the occasion of the International Conference in Guadix, the poster of the pilots and the horizontal work packages (Data analysis, Participatory models and Innovation) were produced, exhibited at the conference, and made available for download from the Digital Poster Gallery on the website.

Figure 39 Posters exhibited at the International Conference in Guadix

5.3 Pilot flyers

Furthermore, the pilots produced flyers devoted to the promotion of the activities within the respective local communities.

Figure 40 Pilot flyers

Furthermore, during the second year, the collection of pilots' Innovation Factsheets was discussed and approved at the project's meeting held in Baza, the sheets were produced to be used locally by the pilot partners, and to be promoted widely making them available for download from the website, together with the general Innovation Factsheet that aggregates highlights from the individual sheets. The documents are accessible in the 'Innovation' page of the INCULTUM website.

5.4 Scientific publications

In addition to the policy outputs that are linked via the Policy page, the pilot products that are linked via the Pilots page, the innovation factsheets that are linked via the Innovation page of the website, the book on participatory approaches of UMB, and the INCULTUM book that is under publication, a very large number of scientific articles and book chapters have been produced by the INCULTUM project, both in English and in national languages. All the papers are available as open access via the Zenodo INCULTUM Community.

A selection of journal articles, posters and chapters books is provided below as a reference to the work done:

- [Senderos culturales a través de acequias históricas en el Altiplano granadino: el proyecto INCULTUM](#): Presentation of the Altiplano de Granada pilot and the activities to be carried out during the INCULTUM project.
- *Survey for online registered users of Historic Graves platform*: This survey is being conducted by Eachtra Archaeological Projects as part of INCULTUM (2021-2024), a tourism-oriented HORIZON2020 funded project. The main goal of this survey was to better understand users and usage of the Historic Graves website and how to improve the visitor experience.
- [Local communities have a right to generate and own tourism related data: Community-led genealogical tourism focused on Irish historic graveyards](#) *Tourist Perceptions of Campina de Faro*: Survey on tourists' familiarity with and associations with the name 'Campina de Faro' carried out in Algarve, Portugal, November 29 – October 2nd
- [Contributo para o estudo dos sistemas de regadio históricos da Campina- Faro, Olhao e Loulé](#): A presente investigação tem como propósito o estudo dos sistemas de regadio históricos existentes na Campina de Faro (Algarve) e a sua relação com a paisagem, cujo valor patrimonial é inegável pela sua singularidade
- [Leisure mobility changes during the COVID-19 pandemic – An analysis of survey and mobile phone data in Sweden](#): The COVID-19 pandemic affected travelling in general, and the leisure mobility and the spatial distribution of travellers in particular. In most parts of the world, both domestic and international travel has been replaced by restrictive policies and recommendations on mobility
- [Inequality in leisure mobility: An analysis of activity space segregation spectra in the Stockholm conurbation](#): This study aims to analyse the inequality dimensions of spatial mobility of individuals who seek to move to recreational and leisure destinations (often 'green' and 'blue') on designated days
- [What you see is where you go: cruise tourists' spatial consumption of destination amenities](#): Using tracking technologies to measure revealed preferences can help detect locations with potential for further expansion or with risks of tourism overgrowth and consequential externalities. Understanding consumer behavior in spatio-temporal dimensions can reveal what contextual factors influence the consumption of a destination
- [Did liberal lockdown policies change spatial behaviour in Sweden? Mapping daily mobilities in Stockholm using mobile phone data during Covid-19](#): Relying on individual responsibility and behavioural nudges, their effectiveness was questioned from the perspective of others who responded with legal restrictions on behaviour

D2.3 Report on communication and dissemination

- [TIC y participación ciudadana como herramientas para la tutela del patrimonio cultural](#): A través de este debate, en el que se han hecho propuestas de diversa índole, hemos podido comprobar como la participación ciudadana es un recurso de uso creciente, en especial para la salvaguarda, divulgación y conocimiento del patrimonio histórico, y además de manera muy diversa, tanto en metodología como en resultados.
- [UMB partnerom H2020 projektu INCULTUM](#): Journal of Economics and Social Research
- *Itinerari di valorizzazione dei beni culturali materiali e immateriali nel territorio del GAL Elimos: Il periodo della dominazione islamica in Sicilia*. Roadbook
- [El paisaje cultural de la Campiña de Faro: Soluciones basadas en el patrimonio del agua y turismo cultural](#): El proyecto europeo INCULTUM tiene en su centro diez casos piloto con el objetivo de explorar el potencial de los territorios periféricos y desatendidos cuando son gestionados por las comunidades locales y las partes interesadas, en el marco del turismo cultural comunitario
- *INCULTUM – Visiting the margins*: A new concept of cultural tourism, based on participation, authenticity, and digital interaction as a response for limiting the negative impacts that touristification implies
- [Η Κοινωνική και Αλληλέγγυα Οικονομία ως παραδοσιακό, αλλά και σύγχρονο εργαλείο ανάπτυξης των ορεινών κοινοτήτων](#): Social and Solidarity Economy as a traditional and modern tool for the development of mountain communities
- *Πολιτισμικός τουρισμός, τεχνολογίες αιχμής και συμμετοχικός σχεδιασμός στο πλαίσιο της Αξιοβίωτης Ολοκληρωμένης Ανάπτυξης*: On an international level, it is becoming increasingly clear that tourism is more than travel and consumption and can be perceived as another way of learning and self-improvement as well as developing a common code of communication with respect to the special characteristics of each distinct culture.

Furthermore, the dataset produces as outputs of the pilot activities (questionnaires and surveys) are all published in the Zenodo INCULTUM Community.

6 MONITORING AND KPIS

Partners have been constantly in contact with the communication leader Promoter to tell about the activities they have been organizing or participating in, reporting their efforts in a shared google sheet

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1QHznsIBlgXhvd6AqoEXtEgc29sdcQhDp28Ex5qEu_os/edit#gid=0

The sheet is organized in three sections:

- online publications, including blogs, webpages, social media posting ...
- events organized or attended, both local meetings and international gatherings
- papers and academic publications

The effectiveness of dissemination and communication has been part of the work conducted in WP7 Impact, evaluation and exploitation plan, which developed in strict coordination with the pilot leaders and the Innovation Manager. The interest raised by stakeholders and research communities has assessed looking at the quality and the persistence of direct contacts, as well as their active participation in the proposed events and their willingness to follow up. The orientation of policy makers in adopting the recommendations distilled from the project's outputs has been another relevant measure, conducted via direct contacts, mostly carried out within the pilots. The ambit of cooperation, opportunities of engagement and upscaling of the interest in the project's methodology and outcomes have been the subject of the work in WP6 Training and networking.

Regarding specifically the communication and dissemination activities, the KPIs related to outreach activities have been monitored with the results illustrated in the table below.

KPI related to Outreach activities established in the GA	Threshold range or unit of measure	Results
No. of international events organised in the course of the 36 months	4	1 International Conference 1 Data workshop 2 Networking sessions (@ Euromed 2022 and @ ESRA 2023 Congress)
No. of local events organised in the course of the 36 months	30	Min. 5 events organised by each of the 10 pilots, including encounters with policy makers, seminars, demonstrations, meeting with communities. Total 50 events
Total no. of people attending the project events	500	Min. 10 participants per local event, reaching out 50 participants by 10 pilots. Total participants in local events: min. 500 Total participants in international events: 110 in presence + 70 online
No. of new cultural events organised in the pilot areas linked with the project	10-15	Total: 17 cultural events in 2023

The monitoring of online access to project's outcomes will continue monitoring the Zenodo INCULTUM Community. The links from the storage of files that were hosted internally in the Wordpress platform where the website was developed, are under migration to ZENODO. The migration has already started to allow the analysis of the access to Zenodo as a measurement of the future impact of the INCULTUM results.

7 CONCLUSIONS

This report provides the overview of the work done during the whole project life cycle.

Because of its nature and concept, the communication and dissemination activities have been conducted as a combination of local and international efforts. At local level, the pilots engaged with local communities and stakeholders to pave the way towards the long-lasting deployment of the innovations experimented during the EU funded period. At international level, the whole consortium has been committed to contribute to the advancement of knowledge.

The questions raised in the pilots and in the research work packages are key and strategic for the EU and worldwide. Overtourism, gentrification, environmental impact of tourism, depopulation of remote areas, are just a few of the major issues that the European society is facing nowadays. INCULTUM has demonstrated that there are possible paths to be explored and the results produced by the project confirm the expectations stated in the proposal. However, it is a long way, where the articulation between local and international remain a key factor.

Communication and dissemination have a very important role and the strategy put in place has delivered what was planned, even exceeding the initial target values. Citizens and stakeholders were informed with clear messages, easily understandable, via the website, the blog, the posters and in the local events, adopting national languages wherever useful. Knowledge and results produced in the pilots and in the policy work were delivered to policy makers and to local public authorities to encourage them to adopt the recommendations distilled from the work done in the project. The research multidisciplinary community was engaged in sharing good practices and lessons learnt.

The INCULTUM project has been designed and executed as a very integrated action, where each work package provided inputs to the others, and was informed by the results of the others. For this reason, the communication and dissemination activities should be read in liaison with the rest of the project, and in particular with the work of the pilots (WP5), the training and networking (WP6, and the impact assessment and exploitation planning (WP7).

All the partners are committed to continuing the outreach efforts for supporting the future deployment of the innovations experimented in INCULTUM.